

Optimizing the Use of Indonesian in Learning in the Digital Era

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ABSTRACT

There needs to be special efforts to increase the use of Indonesian in digital learning. This includes content development, delivery techniques, and utilizing the latest technology that supports the language. Using the literature study method, in this research the author obtained data from books, scientific works, documents and other relevant sources. This research shows how important it is to use Indonesian as best as possible when studying in the digital era. Even though English is considered an international language, especially in the digital world, Indonesian is still a good tool for communicating in learning in Indonesia. Limited Indonesian language resources are one of the main obstacles in this optimization process. The development of Indonesian language educational resources can be a strategic step for parties interested in the world of education in Indonesia. So far, positive student responses show that digital learning can still optimize Indonesian. Therefore, educators, platform developers and policy makers must work together to ensure that Indonesian gets its rightful place in the digital era.

INTRODUCTION

In the era of modern technology, almost every aspect of our lives has been influenced by technology, including education. Conventional learning methods are developing along with advances in information and communication technology (ICT) starting to be replaced by more innovative and interactive approaches, such as e-learning, blended learning, and other technology-based methods (Widodo, 2018). However, one of the challenges that arises in the context of digital-based learning in Indonesia is optimizing the use of Indonesian. There is a tendency that many digital learning resources often use English or other foreign languages, which may be difficult for some Indonesian students to understand (Pratiwi, 2019).

National identity and understanding of citizen's educational concepts are greatly influenced by their national language. (Santoso, 2020). Apart from that, by using Indonesian in digital learning materials, students can better understand and absorb the material presented. In this context, optimizing the use of Indonesian is not only about replacing foreign languages with Indonesian, but also about how to present material in Indonesian that is good, correct and effective for digital learning.

However, it needs to be acknowledged that there is still a gap between the need to optimize the use of Indonesian in digital learning and the availability of resources that support it. According to Hartono (2021), many digital learning content developers in Indonesia prefer to use and apply foreign languages, especially English, for the reason that they are more universal and can reach a wider audience. However, this can certainly ignore the needs of local students who may have difficulty understanding a foreign language.

Therefore, special efforts need to be made to optimize the use of Indonesian in learning in the digital era. Both in terms of content development, delivery methods, and the use of the latest technology that supports the use of Indonesian in the digital learning context. Apart from that, educators also need to be trained in using Indonesian effectively in digital-based learning to improve the quality of education in Indonesia.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Optimization

According to the Big Indonesian Dictionary (KBBI), optimization comes from the word "optimal", which means "best or highest", and "to make better or highest". However, optimization is the process of making something better or better. Therefore, optimization is a process of improving or optimizing something. Therefore, "Optimization" is a term that refers to the process of optimizing something. It is clear that the subject of this research is efforts, actions, or methods to optimize the use of Indonesian when learning in the digital era.

Use of Indonesian

Language is expected to be used by everyone to talk and relate to other people in social interactions. However, generations of the nation have not been able to like the use of Indonesian as a language that unites people. Even the position of Indonesian as a main subject is often underestimated and

considered a boring subject. It is very important to use Indonesian in educational forums because it uses other languages. From Sabang to Merauke, Indonesia is a country rich in culture with various languages in every region.

Learning in the Digital Era

Learning in the digital era refers to an educational process that utilizes information and communication technology (ICT) to support, enrich, improve education, and modify traditional methods of teaching and learning (Setiawan dan Rahardjo, 2017). Digital technology has provided various tools and platforms that enable educators and students to interact in a more flexible and dynamic environment. E-learning, for example, allows access to learning materials anytime and anywhere, breaking down the boundaries of space and time in education (Widodo, 2018).

One of the main characteristics of learning in the digital era is an approach that concentrates on students. Technology provides opportunities for students to control the speed, style and direction of their own learning, thereby making learning more personalized and tailored to individual needs (Hartono, 2021). Additionally, social media and other collaborative platforms promote social learning, where students can share knowledge, discuss ideas, and work together on group projects (Pratiwi, 2019).

Although technology has brought many conveniences and innovations to education, there are also challenges that must be faced. Access issues, the digital divide, and the quality and relevance of content are some of the issues that need to be looked at. In addition, educators need to ensure that technology is used to improve the learning process, not just as an attention-grabbing tool without significant educational substance (Santoso, 2020). Thus, the digital era offers great potential for innovation in education, but it also presents challenges that require critical thinking and creative solutions. To maximize the benefits of technology in learning, educators, policy makers and other stakeholders need to work together to design and implement effective and relevant approaches.

METHODOLOGY

One definition of research methods is the planning process used to carry out research (Surahman et al., 2016). This qualitative research uses a literature study methodology. This research does not require a direct search for field data or research locations because this method collects various data and information from published and unpublished scientific works. Collect data directly from various scientific literature, such as articles, annual reports, books, documents, statistical data, and other sources that are considered related or relevant to the discussion topic (Melfianora, 2019).

The process of conducting library research consists of the following steps:

1. Search and obtain relevant information
2. Selecting significant data
3. Write or highlight important information
4. Re-edit data
5. Displays the obtained data

To conduct this research, a large amount of necessary scientific data was examined. The data collection process must be carried out as well as possible. Apart from that, data must be reliable and accountable (Masturoh & Anggita, 2018). This research uses data processing to reduce and prevent plagiarism. Researchers consider this action to be theft of ideas and previous research findings. However, the researcher emphasized that the writing was his own work. So, there is a need for a minimizing process by processing the data into new data. Plagiarism can also be defined as taking writing or ideas from previous studies without including the author's name.

RESULT AND DISSCUSION

Indonesian is the national language and functions as a symbol of national pride, identity, and communication between cultures and regions. Indonesian has the ability to show cultural and social values that foster our sense of pride as Indonesians. Therefore, we must defend the Indonesian language, our country and our flag as symbols of national identity. Apart from that, Indonesian must be able to unite people from various different tribes, each of whom has a different language and culture. Evidence has shown that this language helps people from different tribes live together.

Indonesian as a national language determines national identity. The use of Indonesian in education makes it easier for the majority of Indonesian students to understand concepts and material (Santoso, 2020). Digital learning still uses foreign languages, especially English. This can also hinder the understanding of students who are less proficient in English (Pratiwi, 2019).

Even though Indonesian is the national language, many e-learning platforms still use English as their main language. This creates barriers for students who are not yet fluent in English. Digital content using Indonesian has a higher acceptance rate among Indonesian students compared to foreign language content. Indonesian language material tends to be less varied than foreign language material. However, when presented well, Indonesian language material has equal or even better learning effectiveness.

Digital learning technologies such as Learning Management Systems (LMS) and other educational applications have started to offer Indonesian language versions. However, the translations provided often still require refinement to be more appropriate to the Indonesian educational context (Widodo, 2018). One of the keys to successful optimization of the use of Indonesian is the teacher's readiness to integrate technology and Indonesian in the learning process. Training for teachers is essential to achieve this goal (Hartono, 2021). Teachers who have been trained to use technology and Indonesian language materials in learning show more positive results in teaching students in the digital era.

The digital era provides great opportunities for education in Indonesia to reach a wider audience and provide more diversified learning materials. However, without optimizing the use of Indonesian, this potential may not be fully realized.

Research shows that students tend to have better understanding when material is taught in their native language. Therefore, optimizing the use of Indonesian in digital content is not only a matter of identity, but also of learning effectiveness. In addition, there is a need to improve the quality of educational technology translations and develop original Indonesian language materials that are in line with the national curriculum.

According to Rahmawati and Sutanto (2022), the importance of using Indonesian in digital learning content. Mother tongue has a positive impact on students' understanding and retention of information. Apart from that, the use of Indonesian in digital content also supports the formation of national identity. However, the challenge is how to develop quality Indonesian language materials that comply with modern educational standards. Investment in teacher training and content developers is key to achieving the desired optimization.

Based on the previous explanation, it can be concluded how important it is to optimize the use of Indonesian in learning in the digital era. Even though English is considered an international language, especially in the digital world, for the learning context in Indonesia, Indonesian remains an effective instrument in delivering material. Meanwhile, limited Indonesian language material is one of the main obstacles to this optimization. Investment in developing Indonesian language learning resources can be a strategic step for parties involved in the world of Indonesian education. Meanwhile, if you look at the positive responses so far from students, it confirms that Indonesian has potential that has not been fully optimized in digital learning. Therefore, educators, platform developers and policy makers must work together to ensure that Indonesian gets its rightful place in the digital era.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Increasing the availability of digital learning materials in Indonesian is very important. In the digital world, English is often considered an international language. However, in education in Indonesia, using Indonesian is better for conveying ideas and helping students understand them. A proof that the use of the mother tongue in the learning process plays an important role in improving the quality of education is the fact that the majority of students in Indonesia respond better to lessons given in Indonesian.

One of the biggest obstacles to optimizing the use of Indonesian is the availability of high-quality content in that language. An important step that must be taken is investment and efforts to increase Indonesian language learning resources. Educators, platform developers, researchers and other parties must work together to improve Indonesian language use in digital learning. Collaborating with various stakeholders will speed up the optimization process.

Thus, this research states that optimizing the use of Indonesian in learning in the digital era is a matter not only of national identity but also the efficiency and effectiveness of the learning process. Indonesian must be prioritized to achieve quality education in the digital era.

FURTHER RESEARCH

This research still has limitations so further research needs to be done on this topic "Optimizing the Use of Indonesian in Learning in the Digital Era".

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